

Figure 1. Mean sperm concentration and percentage motility over time across 12 hormone treatments. Each panel (A–L) displays bar plots of mean sperm concentration (cells/mL) at 0, 1, 3, 5, 7, and 24 hours post injection, overlaid with a dashed line and points representing mean percentage motility. Bars are colored using a log₁₀-scaled viridis color gradient corresponding to sperm concentration. Error bars indicate 95% confidence intervals. Motility was plotted only when sperm were present and total sperm assessed ≥ 10 . Treatments are as follows: A. 5 IU hCG; B. 10 IU hCG; C. 0.3 µg/g GnRH_a; D. 0.6 µg/g GnRH_a; E. 1 µg/g GnRH_a; F. 2 µg/g GnRH_a; G. 3 µg/g GnRH_a; H. 4 µg/g GnRH_a; I. 5 IU hCG + 0.3 µg/g GnRH_a; J. 5 IU hCG + 0.6 µg/g GnRH_a; K. 10 IU hCG + 0.3 µg/g GnRH_a; L. 10 IU hCG + 0.6 µg/g GnRH_a